

Exponential stability for a forecast-assimilation process with unstable dynamics

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Data assimilation, a vital process in areas such as numerical weather prediction, integrates observational data into computational models to provide accurate forecasts. In this study, we conceptualize the forecast-assimilation (FA) process as a dynamic-stochastic system driven by time-dependent observational data. The core objective is to investigate the stability of this process with respect to variations in its initial conditions, particularly when the underlying system dynamics, referred to here as the signal, exhibit instability. We provide a rigorous analysis for both linear and nonlinear dynamics to determine conditions under which the FA process remains stable. In the nonlinear case, we identify an exponential semi-group whose stability is used to prove a uniform in time bound on the expected Wasserstein distance between the true FA process and one that is incorrectly initialized. For linear dynamics, we prove that the FA process converges both weakly and in the Wasserstein topology to a ‘nominal’ one. For this we use a representation of the FA process by means of the classical Kallianpur-Striebel formula. We show that the Wasserstein distance between the FA process correctly initialized and one which is incorrectly initialized converges to 0 exponentially fast provided the wrong initial condition is absolutely continuous with respect to the correct initial condition.

Data assimilation (DA) was introduced in numerical weather prediction during the 1960s to address the absence of a complete set of initial conditions at any given time for the partial differential equations governing large-scale dynamic meteorology¹. Today, it has become an important tool in all the climate sciences, as well as in areas as diverse as the life, physical and socio-economic sciences^{2,3,4,5,6}, as well as in engineering⁷ and finance^{8,9}. It is widely recognized, especially in climate science, that key phenomena are inherently unstable and cause forecasts to diverge without the incorporation of observational corrections^{10,5,11}. Nonetheless, applying judiciously a stream of even partial observations has been shown to permit both short-term prediction and long-term tracking of the system’s behavior^{4,5,12}. The main purpose of the present paper, following up on the work of Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾, is to explain this stability of the so-defined forecast-assimilation (FA) process for unstable dynamics. The assumptions required for these result are less restrictive than those in Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾, allowing for a broader class of nonlinear systems to be analyzed under this framework. In addition the proofs are much more

transparent allowing for a better understanding of the key elements driving the stability and convergence behavior of the system.

I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

A. Background

The primary focus in data assimilation (DA) has been on developing and applying efficient numerical methods to combine the flow of observations, despite their partial and sometimes inaccurate nature, with the system’s temporal evolution, see e.g. Asch, Bocquet, and Nodet⁽¹²⁾ for details. However, significant efforts are also directed toward gaining a deeper understanding of the underlying dynamic processes. To enhance this understanding, various perspectives and approaches have been developed and applied within the DA field. Duane, Tribbia, and Weiss⁽¹⁴⁾ and Abarbanel *et al.*⁽¹⁵⁾, for instance, have suggested to view the FA process as a way of synchronizing the simulation or actual forecasting of the system in a computer with the one occurring in reality — whether in nature, *in vitro* or in another version of the system — where the latter is communicating the observations to the former. Eyink and Restrepo⁽¹⁶⁾ have proposed a number of approaches based on ideas from statistical mechanics, e.g., minimizing an effective action, to track transitions between multiple steady states in a highly nonlinear problem with strong noise, a problem also studied by Miller, Ghil, and Gauthiez⁽¹⁷⁾.

To approach the specific problem addressed herein, namely the prevalent case of systems with unstable dynamics, Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾ have shown that the framework of nonautonomous and random dynamical systems^{18,19,20} may provide an appropriate setting. In practice, this idea turned out to be equivalent to that of

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studying two parallel processes, one being the true signal, the other the FA process that tries to approximate the former one. In the present paper, we pursue this road and attain stronger results with simpler, verifiable assumptions.

B. Outline for DA practitioners

We consider a stochastic signal X_t whose distribution at time t is denoted by p_t which may or may not be stable in a sense described below. We also have an associated observation process Y_t and denote the conditional distribution of X_t given all the observations of Y_s for $0 \leq s \leq t$ by π_t . We think of π_t as a probability measure-valued stochastic process, so that we can view $\pi_t = \lambda_t^{FA} \pi_0$ where

$$\lambda_t^{FA} : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d) \times \Omega \mapsto \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d). \quad (\text{FA})$$

is the push-forward operator of the conditional distribution (see Table I) or the forecast-assimilation (FA) operator. In (FA), Ω is the sample space that incorporates all the random events generated by both the signal and the observation processes and $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ is the space of probability measures on \mathbb{R}^d .

In the following, we assume that the initial conditional distribution π_0 of the signal X_0 coincides with its prior distribution p_0 . This assumption holds, for instance, if no observations are available at time 0, or if Y_0 is either constant or independent of X_0 . Naturally, if this condition is satisfied for all subsequent times, it would imply that $\pi_t = p_t$ for all $t > 0$. However, in this work, we assume otherwise. Specifically, we consider the case where the observations are informative, resulting in π_t being distinct from p_t . Moreover we will look for conditions to ensure that the FA operator, which depends on both the signal dynamics X_t and the observation process Y_t , is stabler than the signal itself, as outlined below.

In this paper, we prove the following stability properties of the FA operator λ_t^{FA} based on the Wasserstein metric:

- A. First, we consider the stability of the FA operator in the nonlinear case. More precisely, we study the discrepancy between the probability measures $\pi_t = \lambda_t^{FA} p_0$ and $\pi_t^\mu := \lambda_t^{FA} \mu$, where μ is an arbitrary probability measure, $\mu \neq p_0$. We show that, under certain conditions, the Wasserstein distance between two probability measures remains bounded in expectation; see Theorem 1 for details. This stability property is valid in the general nonlinear case, with the forecast operator that is possibly unstable.
- B. Second, we investigate the linear case and prove stronger results. As in the first case, we consider the stability of the FA operator; The measures being studied are $\pi_t = \lambda_t^{FA} p_0$ and $\pi_t^\mu := \lambda_t^{FA} \mu$, where μ is an arbitrary probability measure, $\mu \neq p_0$. We show that, under certain conditions on μ , the

Wasserstein distance between π_t and π_t^μ converges to zero. In other words, even if the FA operator is initialized with the wrong initial distribution μ , asymptotically, $\lambda_t^{FA} \mu$ converges to the conditional distribution of the signal, π_t . This stronger stability is investigated in the linear case in Theorem 3. We also consider the Wasserstein distance between $\lambda_t^{FA} p_0$ and $\lambda_t^{FA} \delta_0$, in other words the distance between the conditional distribution of the signal and the forecast assimilation cycle initialized with the Dirac delta measure δ_0 and show that it converges to 0 exponentially fast, see Theorem 4. Moreover, we show that the Wasserstein distance between $\lambda_t^{FA} \mu$ and $\lambda_t^{FA} \delta_0$ converges to 0 exponentially fast under some constraints on the measure μ see Theorem 6. As a consequence also the distance between $\lambda_t^{FA} \mu$ and $\lambda_t^{FA} p_0$ converges to 0 exponentially fast.

The above stability results can be rephrased as follows: Assume that there exists a theoretical algorithm—such as a perfect simulation of the Kushner-Stratonovich equation²¹—that can compute *precisely* the conditional distribution of the signal, given the observational data and the initial condition of the signal. While observations are typically obtained from measuring instruments, the initial distribution of the signal is often unknown or uncertain. In this paper, we investigate whether the computed conditional distribution asymptotically depends on the possibly erroneous initial condition, under Assumptions 1, 2, and 3 of Sec. V. We show that in the nonlinear case, although some dependence on the initial condition may persist, it remains bounded over time. In the linear case, though, this dependence decays exponentially, ultimately vanishing as time progresses due to the accumulated observational evidence.

These results are significant not just from a theoretical perspective, but also from a numerical one, when a numerical filter is used to approximate λ_t^{FA} . Such a numerical approximation is usually initialized with a distribution $\mu \neq p_0$, since the correct p_0 is not known^{1,12,22}. The results here imply that any good proxy $\tilde{\lambda}_t^{FA}$ of the FA process—for example one obtained via numerical approximation—will be expected to converge to the conditional distribution of the signal, even when started from a wrong initial condition and even when the signal is unstable. When the proxy is obtained via a particular numerical approximation, one will need a suitable generalization of the fundamental numerical approximation theorem of differential evolution equations, often called the Lax theorem or the Lax-Richtmyer theorem^{23,24}, to stochastic processes of the type studied herein.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

We give here only a brief review of some known stability results. A lot of work has been done on the stability of nonlinear filters since the 1980s. Crisan

and Ghil⁽¹³⁾ provided a more comprehensive review. Most of the results obtained so far rely on assumptions on the signal that cannot be verified easily since the signals are not observable in practice. For example, some results rely on assumptions of full observability of the signal process, others rely on its ergodicity and/or mixing properties or on restrictive assumptions on the drift term of the stochastic differential equation (SDE) describing the signal. We give below a few details on the assumptions made and the results obtained so far.

Under a fairly restrictive deterministic dynamics $f(X, t)$ of the signal, or forecast process, and linear observation process $h(X_t)$, Stannat⁽²⁵⁾ obtained exponential stability but required additional assumptions on the observability of the processes involved. In this work, f is assumed to be the sum of a linear map and the gradient of a logarithmic map, so that $f = AX + B\nabla \log \phi(X)$ for deterministic matrices A and B , i.e., a very restrictive class of signals and a linear observation process. More recently, Del Moral, Kurtzmann, and Tugaut⁽²⁶⁾ obtained similar results but expanded the family of functions $f(X, t)$ used. In this case, observability assumptions of the processes involved were implemented by assuming bounds on the logarithmic norms of relevant matrices.

Picard⁽²⁷⁾ studied detectability conditions that yield sufficient conditions for uniform stability of the filter subject to additional assumptions on the variance of the noise. Another approach to showing filter stability assumed that the signal is fully observable. Van Handel⁽²⁸⁾ used a stronger formulation of observability and showed it to be a sufficient condition for stability of the nonlinear filter even when the signal is unstable. Chigansky, Liptser, and Van Handel⁽²⁹⁾ provided probabilistic methods that may be used to investigate the stability of the nonlinear filter by exploiting the representation of the processes involved.

Substantial work on the stability of nonlinear filters has been done by assuming the signal to be ergodic. Such an assumption, however, restricts the results to signals that are not unstable and chaotic, while the atmosphere and oceans, for instance, certainly are both^{10,11}. Atar and Zeitouni⁽³⁰⁾ and Atar⁽³¹⁾ investigated exponential stability in Hilbert's projective metric under ergodicity assumptions using tools from the theory of positive operators.

Since ergodicity is not sufficient for the stability of the nonlinear filter, it has been combined with various related assumptions. A common one in the literature is the assumption of good mixing and bounds on the Radon-Nikodym derivatives of the law of the signal. Exponential convergence is proved in this setting in Kleptsyna and Veretennikov⁽³²⁾. Results in the Hilbert projective metric are, however, not very useful to practitioners as they do not offer controls on the moments of the distribution.

Del Moral and Miclo⁽³³⁾ did more work in the ergodic setting but with additional assumptions on the robustness of the signal. More recently, Kim, Mehta, and

Meyn⁷ studied the stability of the filter for a finite or countable state space. In their study, the ergodicity assumption for the signal is further strengthened by the assumption that a Poincaré inequality is satisfied by it; in other words, the signal itself is assumed to be stable. This, in turn, leads to the stability of the filter.

In a separate direction, Crisan and Heine⁽³⁴⁾, instead of imposing ergodicity or regularity conditions on the different maps involved, used assumptions on the tail of the noise distribution in the signal and the observation process.

III. ROUGH MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

In order to illustrate the gist of the problem, we first present the scalar DA version. Since this paper uses signal processing terminology, Table I provides the DA counterpart of this terminology for DA practitioners.

Suppose we have a signal $x(t)$ and an observation process $y(t)$ given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = Ax + u(t), \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = Hx + v(t), \quad (1b)$$

where $u(t)$ and $v(t)$ are white noises with nice properties, such as Gaussian noise. In this case, the FA process corresponds to the best linear unbiased estimate of x and it is given by

$$\frac{d\hat{x}}{dt} = A\hat{x} + K(y - H\hat{x}) \quad (2)$$

or, equivalently, by

$$\frac{d\hat{x}}{dt} = (A - KH)\hat{x} + Ky. \quad (3)$$

In (2) and (3), K corresponds to the Kalman gain, which corresponds in turn, as we shall see, to a covariance matrix in the stochastic case. In (2), $y - H\hat{x}$ is referred to as the innovation vector. Heuristically, it acts as a correction or a forcing term to \hat{x} to compensate for the error due to predicting y by using $H\hat{x}$. In this case, it is possible for the signal x to be unstable with respect to its initial condition, while \hat{x} is stable. This stabilization by the observation process clearly occurs when $A > 0$, while $A - KH < 0$.

In this paper, the best estimate of the signal at a time t is the conditional distribution of the signal given by all the observational data up to t . This conditional distribution is time dependent and it is denoted by π_t , while the distribution of the signal itself at time t is denoted by p_t . A summary of the notation used is given in the next paragraph.

As announced, we denote by p_t^μ and π_t^μ the probability-measured processes that have the same dynamics as

Table I. Comparison of DA and signal processing terms

Notation	Data Assimilation Language	Stochastic Filtering Language
p_t	Probability distribution of the pure forecast	Prior distribution of the signal
π_t	Probability distribution of the FA process	Conditional distribution of the signal
λ_t^F	Forecast operator	Prior distribution operator
λ_t^{FA}	Forecast-Assimilation (FA) operator	Push-forward operator

the signal distribution p_t itself and the conditional distribution π_t , respectively, but they are initialized with $p_0^\mu = \pi_0^\mu = \mu$ with $\mu \neq p_0$. The signal might not be stable, in the sense that p_t and p_t^μ might not get closer to each other as t increases, and we wish to find conditions under which π_t and π_t^μ do converge towards each other. Note that this mutual convergence between π_t and π_t^μ does not necessarily imply that conditional distribution of the signal π_t itself converges, as t tends to infinity, to a probability π_∞ , say.

In contrast to the dynamical system \hat{x} discussed at the start of this section, the dynamical system investigated in this paper is infinite dimensional, since π_t and π_t^μ are probability measures. This makes the analysis much more complicated and techniques such as those used in Arnold⁽³⁵⁾ to demonstrate the stabilizing effect of noise cannot be adapted in a straightforward manner.

In this paper, we estimate the distance between π_t and π_t^μ in the Wasserstein metric. The results depend on whether the dynamics are linear or nonlinear. The results in the linear case are much stronger than in the nonlinear case. In the former case, the distance between π_t and π_t^μ actually tends exponentially to zero, while in the latter case, it is bounded uniformly in time in expectation.

Figure 1 illustrates schematically the situation being studied and the results. We are considering an unstable forecast process, which will initially spread, but eventually exhibit a much reduced Wasserstein distance with respect to an FA process starting from a distinct initial distribution $\mu \neq \pi_0$. For simplicity, in the figure, $\mu \equiv 0$. Note that the figure illustrates the nonlinear case, in which the asymptotic bound on the Wasserstein distance is nonzero, while in the linear case, it is actually zero.

IV. MATHEMATICAL FRAMEWORK

We now introduce the formal setting for our rigorous results. Let the signal X_t be the solution to the following d -dimensional SDE

$$X_t = X_0 + \int_0^t f(X_s)ds + \int_0^t \sigma(X_s)dV_s, \quad (4)$$

where $f : \mathbb{R}^d \mapsto \mathbb{R}^d$ and $\sigma : \mathbb{R}^d \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{d \times p}$ are globally Lipschitz and V_t is a p -dimensional Brownian motion. Under these conditions, (4) has a unique solution; see Karatzas and Shreve⁽³⁶⁾ for details.

In this context, the prior distribution of the signal, p_t , satisfies the following equation

$$p_t(\varphi) := \mathbb{E}(\varphi(X_t)) = p_0(\varphi) + \int_0^t p_s(A\varphi) ds, \quad (5)$$

where the first equality defines p_t for arbitrary measurable functions $\varphi(X_t)$, while the second equality holds when φ is restricted to a suitable family of measurable functions, for example twice differentiable functions with bounded first and second derivatives. For more details on this restriction, see Chapters 2 and 3 in Bain and Crisan⁽³⁷⁾. The operator A is the infinitesimal generator of the signal, i.e.,

$$A\varphi = \sum_{i,j} \frac{1}{2} a_{ij} \partial_i \partial_j \varphi + \sum_i f_i \partial_i \varphi, \quad (6)$$

where $a_{ij} = \sum_k \sigma_{ik} \sigma_{kj}$.

Figure 1. The pure forecast process F (pink color) and the forecast-assimilation process FA (magenta) evolve in the system's n -dimensional phase space $X = \mathbb{R}^n$, while the observations evolve in the d -dimensional space $Y = \mathbb{R}^d$; the evolution here is in continuous time t , while in practice the time is, of necessity, discrete. The corresponding probability measures are p_t for F and π_t for FA , with $\pi_0 = p_0$ at initial time $t = 0$. The distribution of the observations is the blue tube and they are continuously injected into π_t , as illustrated by the blue plane. Courtesy of N. Bodnariuk.

Remark 1. Note that the prior signal p_t , defined by (5) and called here informally the forecast, is deterministic, while the posterior signal π_t , defined below by (11), and called informally the forecast-assimilation process, is stochastic.

The above equation (5) can be recast into a Fokker-Planck equation for the density of p_t under certain conditions. We consider henceforth p_t as a process in $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, the space of probability measures on \mathbb{R}^d . With this notation, we can define the the prior distribution operator associated with (5) as

$$\lambda_t^F : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d) \mapsto \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d), \quad (7a)$$

$$\lambda_t^F p_0 = p_t. \quad (7b)$$

and, in general, for an arbitrary $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $\lambda_t^F \mu := p_t^\mu$, where p_t^μ is the solution of (5) initialized with the measure μ :

$$p_t^\mu(\varphi) = \mu(\varphi) + \int_0^t p_s^\mu(A\varphi) ds, \quad (8)$$

The observation process is defined to be the n -dimensional solution to the SDE

$$Y_t = \int_0^t h(X_s) ds + W_t, \quad (9)$$

where $h : \mathbb{R}^d \mapsto \mathbb{R}^n$ and W_t is a Brownian motion independent of X_0 and V_t . Now let the FA process π_t be the $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ -valued process corresponding to the law of X_t , given all the observations up to time t . Hence, for a measurable map $\varphi : \mathbb{R}^d \mapsto \mathbb{R}$,

$$\pi_t(\varphi) = \mathbb{E}(\varphi(X_t) | Y_s, s \in [0, t]). \quad (10)$$

As in the case of the prior distribution p_t , if the φ 's are restricted to a suitable family of maps, then π_t satisfies the following Kushner-Stratonovich equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_t(\varphi) &= p_0(\varphi) + \int_0^t \pi_s(A\varphi) ds + \int_0^t (\pi_s(\varphi h^\top) \\ &\quad - \pi_s(h^\top)\pi_s(\varphi)) (dY_s - \pi_s(h) ds), \\ &= p_0(\varphi) + \int_0^t \pi_s(A\varphi) ds + \int_0^t (\pi_s(\varphi h^\top) \\ &\quad - \pi_s(h^\top)\pi_s(\varphi)) dI_s, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where

$$I_t := Y_t - \int_0^t \pi_s(h) ds \quad (12)$$

is the innovation process, by analogy with (2). This process is a Brownian motion, see e.g. Bain and Crisan⁽³⁷⁾ for its properties, and thus it is easier to work with analytically. We can thus define a random dynamical system

λ_t^{FA} that corresponds to the random push-forward operator of (11), by analogy with (7), is given by

$$\lambda_t^{FA} : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d) \times \Omega \mapsto \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d), \quad (13a)$$

$$\lambda_t^{FA}(\omega)\pi_0 := \pi_t(\omega). \quad (13b)$$

and, in general, for an arbitrary $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, $\lambda_t^{FA}(\omega)\mu := \pi_t^\mu$, where π_t^μ is the solution of (11) initialized with the measure μ , that is

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_t^\mu(\varphi) &= \mu(\varphi) + \int_0^t \pi_s^\mu(A\varphi) ds + \int_0^t (\pi_s^\mu(\varphi h^\top) \\ &\quad - \pi_s^\mu(h^\top)\pi_s^\mu(\varphi)) (dY_s - \pi_s^\mu(h) ds), \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

We have written $\lambda_t^{FA}(\omega)$ to emphasize that the FA operator is a random operator as opposed to the forecast operator λ_t^F , which is deterministic. For further details on the existence and uniqueness properties of the operator λ^F , see Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾ and Section 2.5 of Karatzas and Shreve⁽³⁶⁾.

We consider the stability of the operator λ^{FA} over the space $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ equipped with the topology induced by the N^{th} Wasserstein metric, defined as follows:

Definition 1. The N^{th} Wasserstein distance between two probability measures $\nu_1, \nu_2 \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ is defined by

$$\mathbb{W}_N(\nu_1, \nu_2) = \inf \left\{ \mathbb{E}(\|Z_1 - Z_2\|^n)^{\frac{1}{n}} \right\}.$$

The infimum in the above formula is taken with respect to all pairs of random variables (Z_1, Z_2) such that $\text{Law}(Z_i) = \nu_i$, with $i = 1, 2$.

As announced in Sec. II, stability is investigated here in Wasserstein metrics to guarantee stability of the n^{th} moments of the forecast process p_t as well. See more on Wasserstein distances and their advantages in Appendix A.

The stability results in this paper are of two types:

- (a) We say that the FA operator is *weakly stable* if there exists a constant $R \geq 0$ such that $\sup_{t \geq 0} \mathbb{E}(\mathbb{W}_2(\lambda_t^{FA} p_0, \lambda_t^{FA} \mu) \leq R)$.
- (b) We say that the FA operator is *N -stable* if $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{W}_N(\lambda_t^{FA} p_0, \lambda_t^{FA} \mu) = 0$.

In this language, we summarize the work done in Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾ as follows:

- (i) Under certain conditions, for a nonlinear (signal-observation) pair, the forecast process is weakly stable (Theorem 3.1 in Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾). Strong conditions on the 8^{th} moments of the covariance matrices of the processes π_t and π_t^μ are required (see B6 in Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾).
- (ii) If the (signal-observation) pair have linear dynamics, the forecast process is *2-stable*. The rates of convergence were not established and the method used were algebraically involved.

In the present paper, we improve on the above with the following results:

- (i) Under certain conditions, for a nonlinear (signal–observation) pair, the forecast process is weakly stable. The conditions used are simpler than above and, for instance, require bounds only on the 2^{nd} moments of π_t and π_t^μ . An additional major assumption (See **Assumption 3**) is also simplified. See the next section for details.
- (ii) For a linear signal–observation pair, the forecast process is N -stable. The rates of convergence are explicitly given and the methods of proofs are simplified considerably.

V. MAIN RESULT FOR NONLINEAR DYNAMICS

First we introduce some notation and a useful lemma used to bound Wasserstein distances. For vectors, we will be using the standard Euclidean norm and for matrices we will be using any norm that is submultiplicative. Note that since our matrices are finite dimensional, the choice of any non-submultiplicative norm would only differ by constants. When dealing with norms of functions, we will be using the supremum norm.

For a measure $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, we use the following notation:

1. **first moments:** $\hat{\mu} = (\hat{\mu}^i)_{i \in 1, \dots, d}$ is the mean vector of μ , i.e.,

$$\hat{\mu} = \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} x \mu(dx), \quad ; \quad |\hat{\mu}| = \left(\sum_{i=1}^d (\hat{\mu}^i)^2 \right)^{1/2}; \quad (15)$$

2. **second moments:** μ^2 is the sum of the second moments of μ , i.e.,

$$\mu^2 = \sum_{i=1}^d \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} x_i^2 \mu(dx); \quad (16)$$

3. **covariance matrix:** $P_\mu = (P_\mu^{ij})_{i,j \in 1, \dots, d}$ is the covariance matrix of μ , i.e.,

$$P_\mu^{ij} = \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} (x_i - \hat{\mu}^i)(x_j - \hat{\mu}^j) \mu(dx), \quad (17a)$$

$$|P_\mu| = \left(\sum_{i,j=1}^d (P_\mu^{ij})^2 \right)^{1/2}. \quad (17b)$$

We will need the following lemma for the proof of the main result. This lemma was also used in Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾.

Lemma 1. *There exists a constant $C = C(d)$ such that, for any $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}^2(\mathbb{R}^d)$,*

$$\begin{aligned} (W_2(\mu, \nu))^2 &\leq C(\mu^2 + \nu^2), \\ W_2(\mu, \nu) &\leq C(|P_\mu|^{1/2} + |P_\nu|^{1/2} + |\hat{\mu} - \hat{\nu}|). \end{aligned}$$

We first make the following assumption on the functions f and h introduced in (4) and (9) respectively.

Assumption 1. *We assume that the functions f and h can be decomposed into a linear part and a bounded nonlinear part:*

$$f = F\mathcal{I} + \tilde{f}, \quad h = H\mathcal{I} + \tilde{h}, \quad (18)$$

where

1. $\mathcal{I} : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ is the identity function defined as $\mathcal{I}(x) = x$ for any $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$;
2. $F \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$, $H \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$ are given matrices; and
3. $\tilde{f} : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, $\tilde{h} : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ are bounded measurable functions.

Note that identity (18) can be rewritten more simply as

$$f(x) = Fx + \tilde{f}(x), \quad h(x) = Hx + \tilde{h}(x), \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^d,$$

but we will need the form (18) in the quantities below.

The above assumption enables \tilde{h} to be integrable with respect to any measure in $\mathcal{P}^2(\mathbb{R}^d)$. This also allows us to bound Lebesgue integrals using $\|\tilde{h}\|_\infty < \infty$ and $\|\tilde{f}\|_\infty < \infty$. For example:

$$\left\| \int_0^t \tilde{h}(X_s) ds \right\| \leq t \|\tilde{h}\|_\infty < \infty.$$

Next we make important assumptions on the covariance matrices associated to π_0 and μ . These assumptions are slightly weaker than those used in Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾, see Assumption 3.

Assumption 2. *The covariance matrices of the processes π^μ and π , respectively, satisfy the uniform bounds:*

$$\sup_{t \geq 0} \mathbb{E}[\|P_t^\mu\|^2] = C^\mu < \infty, \quad \sup_{t \geq 0} \mathbb{E}[\|P_t^{\pi_0}\|^2] = C^{\pi_0} < \infty. \quad (19)$$

We define several quantities that are useful in the proof of the main result, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_s^\mu &:= \pi_s^\mu((\mathcal{I} - \hat{\pi}^\mu)\tilde{h}^\top), \\ \Lambda_s &:= \pi_s((\mathcal{I} - \hat{\pi})\tilde{h}^\top), \\ \varkappa_s^\mu &:= \pi_s^\mu(\mathcal{I}h^\top) - \pi_s^\mu(\mathcal{I})\pi_s^\mu(h^\top) = P_s^\mu H^\top + \Lambda_s^\mu, \\ \varkappa_s &:= \pi_s(\mathcal{I}h^\top) - \pi_s(\mathcal{I})\pi_s(h^\top) = P_s^{\pi_0} H^\top + \Lambda_s. \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2. *Using Assumption 1 and Assumption 2 it is possible to show that there exists positive constants $C^{\varkappa^\mu}, C^{\varkappa}, C^{\Lambda^\mu}, C^\Lambda$ such that*

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{t \geq 0} \mathbb{E}[\|\varkappa_t^\mu\|^2] &= C^{\varkappa^\mu} < \infty, \quad \sup_{t \geq 0} \mathbb{E}[\|\varkappa_t\|^2] = C^{\varkappa} < \infty \\ \sup_{t \geq 0} \mathbb{E}[\|\Lambda_t^\mu\|^2] &= C^{\Lambda^\mu} < \infty, \quad \sup_{t \geq 0} \mathbb{E}[\|\Lambda_t\|^2] = C^\Lambda < \infty. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Assumption 3. Define $Q_s^\mu := F - P_s^\mu H^\top H - \Lambda_s^\mu H$. Assume that Q_s^μ can then be written as $Q_s^\mu = \tilde{Q}_s^\mu + \Delta Q_s^\mu$ where \tilde{Q}_s^μ is assumed to be deterministic and ΔQ_s^μ is random. Further \tilde{Q}_s^μ is assumed to be exponentially stable. That is, if $\psi_{s:t}$ is the solution of the linear matrix ordinary differential equation

$$d_t \psi_{s:t} = \tilde{Q}_t^\mu \psi_{s:t}, \quad \psi_{s:s} = I,$$

where I is the identity matrix, then there exist two constants $0 < c < C$ such that for any function ϕ

$$e^{-C(t-s)} \|\phi\| \leq \|\psi_{s:t} \phi\| \leq e^{-c(t-s)} \|\phi\| \quad (21)$$

Moreover, note that $\psi_{s:t}^{-1}$ is the solution of the linear matrix ordinary differential equation

$$d_t \psi_{s:t}^{-1} = -\psi_{s:t}^{-1} \tilde{Q}_t^\mu, \quad \psi_{s:s} = I,$$

where I is the identity matrix and we deduce from (21) that for any ϕ

$$e^{c(t-s)} \|\phi\| \leq \|\psi_{s:t}^{-1} \phi\| \leq e^{C(t-s)} \|\phi\| \quad (22)$$

Finally assume that ΔQ_s^μ is bounded on every $[0, s]$ by a constant independent of s :

$$\|\Delta Q_s^\mu\| \leq K \quad (23)$$

for some $K > 0$, such that $K < c$.

Remark 3. In Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾ the following further assumption was made:

There exists $\delta > 0$ such that

$$\int_{k\delta}^{(k+1)\delta} \mathbb{E} \left[|\psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1}|^4 \right] ds \leq C^{inv},$$

where C^{inv} is a constant independent of k . This assumption is not easy to verify.

Theorem 1. Let p_0 and μ be elements of $\mathcal{P}^2(\mathbb{R}^d)$. Then under **Assumption 1**, **Assumption 2** and **Assumption 3**, the FA operator is weakly stable, in particular there exists a constant $R > 0$ independent of t such that:

$$\mathbb{E} [\mathbb{W}_2(\pi_t^\mu, \pi_t)] \leq R \quad (24)$$

The proof of this result is given in the appendix. The proof relies on using Lemma 1 and Assumption 2, so that showing that the FA process is weakly stable is equivalent to proving that the difference in the means of π_t and π_t^μ is bounded in expectation. In order to control this difference, we make use of (11). The nonlinear terms in this expression are controlled via Assumption 2, while Assumption 3 helps us ensure that the linear terms generate a stable exponential semi-group.

In order to prove that $\mathbb{W}_2(\pi_t^\mu, \pi_t)$ is bounded in expectation, we first prove the result on a suitably chosen discrete unbounded grid of times t_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots$, and then

within each interval (t_i, t_{i+1}) . The grid selection differs from that in Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾, where the grid was specifically chosen to enable us to use the additional assumption stated in Remark 3. Furthermore, in the proof of the theorem, we no longer rely on a control based on the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality. Instead, we use inequalities (21) and (23), which are part of Assumption 3.

We note that the stability result in the non-linear case is significantly weaker than that in the linear case, despite the strength of the assumptions imposed on the coefficients. The perturbations away from the linear case through the bounded functions \tilde{f} and \tilde{h} , while seemingly innocent enough, are not likely to allow for stronger results. Nevertheless, the assumptions cover non-ergodic and unstable signals. For example, if the matrix F appearing in the decomposition of the drift term of the signal has positive eigenvalues, then it is unlikely that the signal will have ergodicity or stability properties. We gave a simple example along these lines in the earlier paper of Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾.

If no observations are available, then the Forecast-Assimilation operator and the Forecast operator coincide. In the linear case, we can model this by assuming that the matrix H appearing in the observation equation (25b) below is 0, in other words the observation is just noise that is independent of the signal. In this case, the distance between $\lambda_t^{FA} p_0 = \lambda_t^F p_0$ and $\lambda_t^{FA} \mu = \lambda_t^F \mu$ will converge to 0 provided the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process X described by equation (25a) is stable. This will occur if the maximal eigenvalue of F is negative. In the motivational, one-dimensional example in Section III, this reduces to the assumption that the scalar A is negative. Similarly, in the non-linear case, we can assume that h , H and \tilde{h} are all 0. In this case, $\lambda_t^{FA} p_0 = \lambda_t^F p_0$ and $\lambda_t^{FA} \mu = \lambda_t^F \mu$ will be weakly stable if the matrix F leads to an exponentially stable semi-group so that inequality (22) holds and, therefore, so does Assumption 3.

VI. MAIN RESULTS WITH LINEAR DYNAMICS

The purpose of this section is to prove that regardless of the initial condition, the optimal filter converges to the same distribution both weakly and in the Wasserstein distance. Weak convergence was proved in Ocone and Pardoux⁽³⁸⁾ however the proof presented here is different: it is more concise and does not require the computation of the densities and transport operator Q which will be introduced below. For the convergence and stability results in Wasserstein topology, exponential decay rates are obtained.

We introduce first some notation and some familiar processes that are useful in linear case. Throughout this section $f(X_s) = FX_s$ in (4) and $h(X_s) = HX_s$ in (9). F and H are a constant matrices of appropriate dimensions ($d \times d$ and $n \times d$ respectively). Consider the

following signal-observation model:

$$X_t = \int_0^t FX_s ds + CV_t \quad (25a)$$

$$Y_t = \int_0^t HX_s ds + W_t, \quad (25b)$$

where C is a $d \times d$ matrix. As above, we let

$$\pi_t(\phi) = \mathbb{E}(\phi(X_t) | Y_s, s \in [0, t]). \quad (26)$$

Let $(m_t(x, R), \psi_t(R))$ be the solution to the Kalman filtering equations started at (x, R) . That is $m_t(x, R)$ satisfies the coupled equations:

$$\begin{cases} dm_t(x, R) = Fm_t(x, R)dt + \psi_t(R)H^\top[dY_t \\ -Hm_t(x, R)dt], & m_0(x, R) = x \\ d\psi_t(R) = F\psi_t(R) + \psi_t(R)F^\top + CC^\top \\ -\psi_t(R)H^\top H\psi_t(R), & \psi_0(R) = R \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

It is well known then that π_t^x is Gaussian with mean $m_t(x, R)$ and covariance matrix $\psi_t(R)$. Next consider the exponential semigroup defined by

$$d\mathcal{E}_{s,t}(R) = (F - \psi_t(R)H)\mathcal{E}_{s,t}(R)dt, \quad \mathcal{E}_{s,s}(R) = 1 \quad (28)$$

When $s = 0$, we write $\mathcal{E}_{0,t}(R) = \mathcal{E}_t(R)$. Then it follows that

$$m_t(x, R) = x\mathcal{E}_t(R) + \int_0^t \mathcal{E}_{s,t}(R)\psi_s(R)H^\top dY_s \quad (29)$$

and it is clear that $\int_0^t \mathcal{E}_{s,t}(R)\psi_s(R)H^\top dY_s = m_t(0, R)$

Next recall from the Kallianpur-Striebel formula, see Bain and Crisan⁽³⁷⁾, we can write

$$\pi_t(\phi) = \frac{\rho_t(\phi)}{\rho_t(1)}, \quad (30)$$

where ρ_t is the unnormalised conditional distribution. In particular, one can show that

$$\rho_t(1) = 1 + \int_0^t \rho_s(H)dY_s, \quad (31)$$

and hence

$$\rho_t(1) = 1 + \int_0^t \rho_s(1)\pi_s(H)dY_s. \quad (32)$$

It is then possible to change probability measure so that Y_s is a Brownian motion and under this measure it follows that

$$\rho_t(1) = \exp\left(\int_0^t \pi_s(H)dY_s - \frac{1}{2}\int_0^t \pi_s(H^\top)\pi_s(H)ds\right). \quad (33)$$

Denote now by Q_t the transport sending π_0 to ρ_t , that is $\pi_0 Q_t(\phi) = \rho_t(\phi)$. In other words it is the evolution operator evolving the filter from its initial state to its

un-normalised state at time t . If we replace π_0 by δ_{x_0} , where δ_{x_0} is a delta distribution at centered x_0 , by $\pi_0 = \delta_{x_0}$ we write $\delta_{x_0} Q_t(\phi) := Q_t(\phi)(x_0)$ to make the dependence on x_0 explicit.

We give below a key lemma that is used in the proofs of this section. The proof of this result relies on an alternate definition of the Wasserstein distance, see Appendix A for a proof and Villani⁽³⁹⁾, Chapter 2.

Lemma 2. *Let μ_1 and μ_2 be two probability measures with finite n^{th} moment and let M be a Markov transition kernel. Then*

$$\mathbb{W}_N(\mu_1 M, \mu_2 M) \leq \int \int \mu_1(dx_1)\mu_2(dx_2)\mathbb{W}_N(\delta_{x_1}M, \delta_{x_2}M)$$

Finally we recall one of the classical results available on the stability of the Riccati equation associated with the Kalman filter. The form of the result here is the same one used in Atar and Zeitouni⁽³⁰⁾. For a matrix M , we denote the largest eigenvalue of M by $\zeta(M)$. If $\zeta(M)$ is negative then we say that M is stable.

Theorem 2. *If the pair of matrices (A, B) is stabilizable and the pair (A, C) is detectable, the algebraic Riccati equation:*

$$C^\top C + PA + A^\top P + PBB^\top P = 0$$

has a unique solution $P = P_\infty$ such that $Q_\infty = A - P_\infty BB^\top$ is stable. If

$$\frac{dP_t}{dt} = C^\top C + P_t A + A^\top P_t + P_t B B^\top P_t,$$

then, for all $0 \leq -a < -\zeta(Q_\infty)$, there exists a constant K_a such that

$$\|P_t - P_\infty\| \leq K_a e^{-at}.$$

This theorem is the key result that ensures that the exponential semigroup defined in (28) decays.

Proposition 1. *If the conditions of Theorem 1 are satisfied, then there exists a positive constant σ and a time $T > 0$ such that:*

$$\|\mathcal{E}_t(0)\| \leq e^{-\sigma t}$$

for all $t > T$.

The main idea is to show that the optimal filter (π_t) can be decomposed into an integral over π_0 and a Gaussian transition kernel.

Proposition 2. *Let $\phi : \mathbb{R}^N \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ be any function that is π_t integrable and let Q_t be as defined previously. Then:*

$$\pi_t(\phi) = \int \frac{\pi_0(dx_0)Q_t(1)(x_0)}{\pi_0 Q_t(1)} \pi_t^{x_0, 0}(\phi). \quad (34)$$

Proof. We have that,

$$\pi_t(\phi) = \frac{\pi_0 Q_t(\phi)}{\pi_0 Q_t(1)} \quad (35)$$

$$= \int \frac{\pi_0(dx_0) \delta_{x_0} Q_t(\phi)}{\pi_0 Q_t(1)} \frac{\delta_{x_0} Q_t(1)}{\delta_{x_0} Q_t(1)} \quad (36)$$

$$= \int \frac{\pi_0(dx_0) Q_t(1)(x_0)}{\pi_0 Q_t(1)} \pi_t^{x_0,0}(\phi) \quad (37)$$

since $\pi_t^{x_0,0}(\phi) = \frac{\delta_{x_0} Q_t(\phi)}{\delta_{x_0} Q_t(1)}$. \square

Recall now that $\pi_t^{x_0,0}$ has the same law as a Gaussian with mean $m_t(x_0, 0)$ and variance $\psi(x_0, 0)$ and is associated with the Gaussian transition kernel

$$G(du, x_0) := \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\psi_t(x_0, 0)}} e^{-\frac{(u-x_0)^2}{2\psi_t(x_0, 0)}} du.$$

With this notation, we can then write (34) as:

$$\pi_t(\phi) = \int \int \frac{\pi_0(dx_0) Q_t(1)(x_0)}{\pi_0 Q_t(1)} G(du, x_0) \phi(u). \quad (38)$$

Now consider the filter started at $(x, R) = (0, 0)$ and let its solution be $\pi_t^{0,0}$. Observe also that

$$\frac{\pi_0(dx_0) Q_t(1)(x_0)}{\pi_0 Q_t(1)}$$

is the law of X_0 given \mathcal{Y}_t . Combining this observation with (38), we obtain the representation

$$\pi_t = \text{Law}(X_0 | \mathcal{Y}_t) G.$$

This representation is understood in the sense that:

$$\pi_t(\phi) = \int \int \phi(u) G(du, x) \text{Law}(X_0 | \mathcal{Y}_t)(dx).$$

Using the above, we obtain the result of Ocone and Pardoux⁽³⁸⁾ :

Theorem 3. *Let $\phi_t : \mathbb{R}^N \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ be a bounded uniformly continuous function. Then if $\mathbb{E}(X_0^2 | \mathcal{Y}_t) < \infty$ we have*

$$|\pi_t(\phi) - \pi_t^{0,0}(\phi)| \rightarrow 0. \quad (39)$$

Considering Lemma 2, we prove that the n -Wasserstein distance between π_t and $\pi_t^{0,0}$ tends to 0 exponentially fast.

Theorem 4. *For any $n \geq 1$, if $\mathbb{E}(X_0 | \mathcal{Y}_t) < \infty$, then there exists $T > 0$*

$$\mathbb{W}_N(\pi_t, \pi_t^{0,0}) \leq \mathbb{E}(X_0 | \mathcal{Y}_t) e^{-\sigma t} \quad (40)$$

for some $0 < \sigma < -\zeta(A - \psi_\infty H^\top H)$ and for all $t > T$.

In the remainder of this section we assume that while X_0 has initial distribution π_0 , the wrong initial condition $\pi_0^\mu := \mu$ is used which generates the distributions π_t^μ at time t . We further assume that μ is absolutely continuous with respect to π_0 such that it admits a density $g(dx)$ with respect to π_0 which is integrable with respect to π_0 . With this notation we can write

$$\pi_t^\mu(\phi) = \int \frac{\pi_0^\mu(dx_0) Q_t(1)(x_0)}{\pi_0^\mu Q_t(1)} \pi_t^{x_0,0}(\phi) \quad (41)$$

and

$$\pi_t^\mu(\phi) = \int \frac{g(x_0) \pi_0(dx_0) Q_t(1)(x_0)}{\pi_0 Q_t(1)} \pi_t^{x_0,0}(\phi). \quad (42)$$

To get to the second identity we have used that

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_t^\mu Q_t(1) &= \int \pi_0^\mu(dx_0) \exp\left(\int_0^t \pi^{x_0,0}(H) dY_s\right) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \int \pi_s^{x_0,0}(H^\top) \pi_s^{x_0,0}(H) ds \\ &= \int g(x_0) \pi_0(dx_0) \exp\left(\int_0^t \pi^{x_0,0}(H) dY_s\right) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \int \pi_s^{x_0,0}(H^\top) \pi_s^{x_0,0}(H) ds \\ &= \pi_t(g) = \pi_0 Q_t(g). \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

We can also write

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_0 Q_t(g) &= \pi_0 Q_t(1) \frac{\pi_0 Q_t(g)}{\pi_0 Q_t(1)} \\ &= \pi_0 Q_t(1) \mathbb{E}(g(X_0) | \mathcal{Y}_t). \end{aligned}$$

We get the following results:

Theorem 5. *Let $\phi_t : \mathbb{R}^N \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ be a bounded uniformly continuous function. Then if $\mathbb{E}(g(X_0)) < \infty$ and $\mathbb{E}(g(X_0) | X_0|^2) < \infty$ we have*

$$|\pi_t^\mu(\phi) - \pi_t^{0,0}(\phi)| \rightarrow 0. \quad (44)$$

Theorem 6. *For any $n \geq 1$, if $\mathbb{E}(|X_0|) < \infty$ and $\mathbb{E}(|X_0| g(X_0)) < \infty$, then there exists $T > 0$ such that*

$$\mathbb{W}_N(\pi_t^\mu, \pi_t^{0,0}) \leq \mathbb{E} \left(\frac{g(X_0) |X_0| |\mathcal{Y}_t|}{\mathbb{E}(g(X_0) | \mathcal{Y}_t)} \right) e^{-\sigma t} \quad (45)$$

for some $0 < \sigma < -\zeta(A - \psi_\infty H^\top H)$ and for all $t > T$. As a consequence, the FA operator is n -stable.

The results presented above improve on those of Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾ and streamline the arguments used therein, as well as those in Ocone and Pardoux⁽³⁸⁾. In particular, the results of Crisan and Ghil⁽¹³⁾ showed convergence in \mathbb{W}_2 only and did not provide an explicit rate of convergence. Here we have established the exponential rate of convergence, as well as an explicit constant. Furthermore, the methods used herein do not require any explicit computation of the operator Q .

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Appendix A: Wasserstein distances

Much work has been done in looking at the stability of filters, however most results are in the Hilbert metric, total-variation metric, Hellinger distance, weighted-total variation distance, and Wasserstein metrics, amongst others. These metrics are not all equally convenient, since they do not all guarantee the convergence of the moments of π_t . While convergence in the total variation metric is stronger than weak convergence, (that is $\mu_n f \rightarrow \mu f$, for bounded, continuous f in the weak case and $\mu_n f \rightarrow \mu f$ for bounded, measurable f in the total variation metric), for unbounded functions $\mu_n f$ might not converge to μf when $\|\mu_n - \mu\|_{TV} \rightarrow 0$. For example:

$$\mu_n = \delta_0 \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right) + \delta_n \frac{1}{n} \quad \mu(0) = \delta_0.$$

Then $\|\mu_n - \mu\|_{TV} = \frac{1}{n} \rightarrow 0$. However, if f is the identity map, $\int f d\mu_n = 1 \neq \int f d\mu = 0$. This does not apply to the topology induced by the \mathbb{W}_2 distance. More

precisely, for measures μ_n, μ with finite second moments, $\mathbb{W}_2(\mu_n, \mu) \rightarrow 0$ if and only if μ_n converges weakly and their first and second moments converge as well. In other words (see Theorem 6.9 Villani⁽³⁹⁾):

We have that μ_n converges in the topology induced by \mathbb{W}_2 if and only if for all continuous functions φ with $|\varphi(x)| \leq C(1+x^2)$, $C \in \mathbb{R}$, one has

$$\int \varphi(x) d\mu_k(x) \longrightarrow \int \varphi(x) d\mu(x).$$

Thus \mathbb{W}_2 metrizes the weak topology on the space of measures with finite first and second moments. The Wasserstein metric is not the only metric offering such convenient properties. In fact, it can be controlled by using the weighted total variation metric.

$$\mathbb{W}_2(\mu_n, \mu) \leq \sqrt{2} \left(\int \|x\|^2 d|\mu_n - \mu|(x) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (\text{A1})$$

See Theorem 6.15 in Villani⁽³⁹⁾ and in general Chapter 6 for details. Finally we recall a dual characterisation of the Wasserstein distance and prove a factorisation lemma.

$$\mathbb{W}_N(P, Q) = \sup_{\psi, \phi} \int \psi(x) P(dx) + \int \psi(y) Q(dy), \quad (\text{A2})$$

where the supremum is taken over all bounded continuous ψ, ϕ such that

$$\psi(x) + \phi(y) \leq \|x - y\|^n.$$

When we write sup in the proof below, it is understood to be over this set of functions. See Theorem 5.10 in Villani⁽³⁹⁾. We give next the proof of Lemma 2:

Proof of Lemma 2. The proof of the lemma relies on the dual characterisation of the Wasserstein distance.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{W}_N &= \sup \left[\int \psi(x) \mu_1(dz_1) M(z_1, dx) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int \phi(y) \mu_2(dz_2) M(z_2, dy) \right] \\ &= \sup \left[\int \phi(x) \mu_1(dz_1) M(z_1, dx) \mu_2(dz_2) K(z_2, dy) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int \psi(y) \mu_1(dz_1) M(z_1, dx) \mu_2(dz_2) K(z_2, dy) \right] \\ &= \sup \left[\int \mu_1(dz_1) \mu_2(dz_2) \left(\int \phi(x) M(z_1, dx) M(z_2, dy) \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int \psi(y) M(z_1, dx) M(z_2, dy) \right] \\ &\leq \int \mu_1(dz_1) \mu_2(dz_2) \left(\sup \left[\int \phi(x) M(z_1, dx) M(z_2, dy) \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int \psi(y) M(z_1, dx) M(z_2, dy) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A3})$$

Carrying out the integral in y in the penultimate integral and the one in x in the last integral gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{W}_N &\leq \int \mu_1(dz_1) \mu_2(dz_2) \left(\sup \left[\int \phi(x) M(z_1, dx) \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + \int \psi(y) M(z_1, dx) \right] \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A4})$$

Since

$$\int \phi(x) M(z_1, dx) = \int \int \phi(x) \delta_{z_1}(dx') M(x', dx)$$

and

$$\int \psi(y) M(z_2, dy) = \int \int \psi(y) \delta_{z_2}(dx') M(x', dy),$$

the result follows. \square

Appendix B: Proof of main nonlinear result

Theorem 3. *Let π_0 and μ be elements of $(\mathcal{P}^2(\mathbb{R}^d))$. Then under Assumption 1, Assumption 2 and Assumption 3 there exists a constant $R > 0$ independent of t such that:*

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{W}_2(\pi_t^\mu, \pi_t)] \leq R \quad (\text{B1})$$

Proof. The proof relies on using Lemma 1 and Assumption 2, so that proving that the FA process is weakly stable is equivalent to proving that the difference in the means of π_t and π_t^μ is bounded in expectation. To do this, let k be an arbitrary integer and $\delta > 0$ be a fixed real number which we will specify later. Both $\hat{\pi}_t^\mu$ and $\hat{\pi}_t$ satisfy the Kushner-Stratonovich equation. We begin by writing down the two relevant equations and make substitutions for the innovation process using (12). We get for $t \in [k\delta, (k+1)\delta]$:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\pi}_t^\mu &= \hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu + \int_{k\delta}^t \pi_s^\mu(f) ds + \int_{k\delta}^t \mathcal{Z}_s^\mu(dY_s - \pi_s^\mu(h) ds), \\ \hat{\pi}_t^\mu &= \hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu + \int_{k\delta}^t \pi_s^\mu(f) ds + \int_{k\delta}^t \mathcal{Z}_s^\mu(dI_s \\ &\quad + (\pi_s(h) - \pi_s^\mu(h)) ds), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B2})$$

$$\hat{\pi}_t = \hat{\pi}_{k\delta} + \int_{k\delta}^t \pi_s(f) ds + \int_{k\delta}^t \mathcal{Z}_s dI_s. \quad (\text{B3})$$

Replacing the observation process Y_t by the innovation process I_t in the evolution equations for $\hat{\pi}_t^\mu$ and $\hat{\pi}_t$ is important: Unlike Y_t , I_t is a standard Brownian motion, which enables us to use classical stochastic calculus properties to bound the moments of the stochastic integrals. Next, by taking the difference between (B2) and (B3),

we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\pi}_t^\mu - \hat{\pi}_t &= (\hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{k\delta}) \\
&\quad - \int_{k\delta}^t (\pi_s^\mu - \pi_s) (f - \mathcal{X}_s^\mu \tilde{h}) ds + \int_{k\delta}^t (\mathcal{X}_s^\mu - \mathcal{X}_s) dI_s \\
&= (\hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{k\delta}) + \int_{k\delta}^t Q_s^\mu (\hat{\pi}_s^\mu - \hat{\pi}_s) ds \\
&\quad + \int_{k\delta}^t (P_s^\mu - P_s) H^\top dI_s + z_{k\delta:t}^\mu,
\end{aligned}$$

where $z_{k\delta:t}^\mu$ is a process that contains the nonlinear terms in the evolution equation of $\hat{\pi}^\mu - \hat{\pi}$, that is

$$z_{k\delta:t}^\mu = \int_{k\delta}^t (\pi_s^\mu - \pi_s) (\tilde{f} - \mathcal{X}_s^\mu \tilde{h}) ds + \int_{k\delta}^t (\Lambda_s^\mu - \lambda_s) dI_s. \quad (\text{B4})$$

Next we apply integration by parts to $\psi_{k\delta:t}^{-1} (\hat{\pi}_t^\mu - \hat{\pi}_t)$ for $t \in [k\delta, (k+1)\delta]$ to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\psi_{k\delta:t}^{-1} (\hat{\pi}_t^\mu - \hat{\pi}_t) \\
&= (\hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{k\delta}) + \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} (P_s^\mu - P_s) H^\top dI_s \\
&\quad + \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} dz_s^\mu + \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} \Delta Q_s^\mu (\hat{\pi}_s^\mu - \hat{\pi}_s) ds. \quad (\text{B5})
\end{aligned}$$

We then multiply (B5) by $\psi_{k\delta:t}$ and take the expected value of the norm of $\hat{\pi}_t^\mu - \hat{\pi}_t$. Using (B5) and the triangle inequality, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_t^\mu - \hat{\pi}_t\|] \\
&\leq \mathbb{E} [\|\psi_{k\delta:t} (\hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{k\delta})\|] \\
&\quad + \mathbb{E} \left[\|\psi_{k\delta:t} \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} (P_s^\mu - P_s) H^\top dI_s\| \right] \\
&\quad + \mathbb{E} \left[\|\psi_{k\delta:t} \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} dz_s^\mu\| \right] \\
&\quad + \mathbb{E} \left[\|\psi_{k\delta:t} \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} \Delta Q_s^\mu (\hat{\pi}_s^\mu - \hat{\pi}_s) ds\| \right] \quad (\text{B6})
\end{aligned}$$

Next we proceed to bound each term in (B6). The first term is readily bounded using (21) and gives:

$$\mathbb{E} [\|\psi_{k\delta:t} (\hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{k\delta})\|] \leq e^{-c(t-k\delta)} \mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{k\delta}\|]. \quad (\text{B7})$$

For the second term in (B6), we make use of (21), (22), Jensen's inequality and Itô's isometry to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \psi_{k\delta:t} \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} (P_s^\mu - P_s) H^\top dI_s \right\| \right] \\
&\leq \|\psi_{k\delta:t}\| \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} (P_s^\mu - P_s) H^\top dI_s \right\|^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&\leq e^{-c(t-k\delta)} \mathbb{E} \left[\int_{k\delta}^t \|\psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} (P_s^\mu - P_s) H^\top\|^2 ds \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&\leq e^{-c(t-k\delta)} \left(\int_{k\delta}^t \|\psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1}\|^2 \mathbb{E} [\|(P_s^\mu - P_s) H^\top\|^2] ds \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&\leq C_1 e^{(C-c)(t-k\delta)} \sqrt{\delta} \quad (\text{B8})
\end{aligned}$$

since

$$\sqrt{\mathbb{E} [\|(P_s^\mu - P_s) H^\top\|^2]} \leq \|H\| \sqrt{2(C^{P^\mu} + C^{\pi_0})} =: C_1$$

For the third term in (B6), we first split it into two terms which we each bound separately.

$$\begin{aligned}
&\psi_{k\delta:t} \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} dz_s^\mu \\
&= \psi_{k\delta:t} \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} (\pi_s^\mu - \pi_s) (\tilde{f} - \mathcal{X}_s^\mu \tilde{h}) ds \\
&\quad + \psi_{k\delta:t} \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} (\pi_s^\mu - \pi_s) (\tilde{f} - \mathcal{X}_s^\mu \tilde{h}) (\Lambda_s^\mu - \lambda_s) dI_s \quad (\text{B9})
\end{aligned}$$

For the first term in (B9), first note the following using Remark 2:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sup_{t \geq 0} \mathbb{E} (\|\tilde{f} - \mathcal{X}_t^\mu \tilde{h}\|) &\leq \sup_{t \geq 0} \mathbb{E} (\|\tilde{f}\| + \|\mathcal{X}_t^\mu \tilde{h}\|) \\
&\leq \|\tilde{f}\| + \|\tilde{h}\| \sup_{t \geq 0} \sqrt{\mathbb{E} (\|\mathcal{X}_t^\mu\|^2)} \\
&\leq \|\tilde{f}\| + \|\tilde{h}\| \sqrt{C^{\mathcal{X}^\mu}} = C_2 \quad (\text{B10})
\end{aligned}$$

Then we use as before (21), (22) and (B10). It follows that:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \psi_{k\delta:t} \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} (\pi_s^\mu - \pi_s) (\tilde{f} - \mathcal{X}_s^\mu \tilde{h}) ds \right\| \right] \\
&\leq e^{(C-c)(t-k\delta)} \delta C_2. \quad (\text{B11})
\end{aligned}$$

For the second term in (B9), we proceed similarly to (B8) and use the fact that there exists a constant C_3 such that $\sup_{t \geq 0} \mathbb{E} (\|(\tilde{f} - \mathcal{X}_s^\mu \tilde{h}) (\Lambda_s^\mu - \lambda_s)\|^2) \leq (C_3)^2$. This yields:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \psi_{k\delta:t} \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} (\pi_s^\mu - \pi_s) (\tilde{f} - \mathcal{X}_s^\mu \tilde{h}) (\Lambda_s^\mu - \lambda_s) dI_s \right\| \right] \\
&\leq e^{(C-c)(t-k\delta)} \sqrt{\delta} C_3 \quad (\text{B12})
\end{aligned}$$

For the final term of (B5), we use (23) and similar methods to before. This gives:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \psi_{k\delta:t} \int_{k\delta}^t \psi_{k\delta:s}^{-1} \Delta Q_s^\mu (k+1) (\hat{\pi}_s^\mu - \hat{\pi}_s) ds \right\| \right] \\
&\leq K \int_{k\delta}^t e^{-c(t-k\delta)} e^{C(s-k\delta)} \mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_s^\mu - \hat{\pi}_s\|] ds \quad (\text{B13})
\end{aligned}$$

Taking norms, using the triangle inequality, taking expectations and using our estimates gives:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_t^\mu - \hat{\pi}_t\|] \\
&\leq e^{-c(t-k\delta)} \mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{k\delta}\|] \\
&\quad + e^{(C-c)(t-k\delta)} (\sqrt{\delta} (C_1 + C_3) + \delta C_2) \\
&\quad + K \int_{k\delta}^t e^{-c(t-k\delta)} e^{C(s-k\delta)} \mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_s^\mu - \hat{\pi}_s\|] ds \quad (\text{B14})
\end{aligned}$$

Let

$$F(s) := e^{c(s-k\delta)} \mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_s^\mu - \hat{\pi}_s\|]$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} F(t) &\leq F(k\delta) + e^{C(t-k\delta)} (\sqrt{\delta}(C_1 + C_3) + \delta C_2) \\ &\quad + K \int_{k\delta}^t e^{(C-c)(s-k\delta)} F(s) ds \\ &\leq F(k\delta) + e^{C\delta} (\sqrt{\delta}(C_1 + C_3) + \delta C_2) \\ &\quad + K e^{(C-c)\delta} \int_{k\delta}^t F(s) ds \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B15})$$

So, by Gronwall's inequality, we deduce that

$$F(t) \leq \left(F(k\delta) + e^{C\delta} (\sqrt{\delta}(C_1 + C_3) + \delta C_2) \right) e^{K e^{(C-c)\delta} (t-k\delta)} \quad (\text{B16})$$

Finally, by introducing (B16) into (B15) we get that

$$F(t) \leq F(k\delta) (1 + \delta K C_4(\delta)) + C_5(\delta)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} C_4(\delta) &= e^{(C-c)\delta + K e^{(C-c)\delta} \delta} \\ c_4(\delta) &= (\sqrt{\delta}(C_1 + C_3) + \delta C_2) \\ C_5(\delta) &= e^{C\delta} c_4(\delta) \\ &\quad + \delta K e^{(C-c)\delta} (e^{C\delta} c_4(\delta)) e^{K e^{(C-c)\delta} \delta} \end{aligned}$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_t^\mu - \hat{\pi}_t\|] &\leq e^{-c(t-k\delta)} (\mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{k\delta}\|] \\ &\quad \times (1 + \delta K C_4(\delta)) + C_5(\delta)) \\ &\leq e^{-(c-KC_4(\delta))(t-k\delta)} \mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{k\delta}\|] \\ &\quad + C_5(\delta) e^{-c\delta} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B17})$$

and, in particular,

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \hat{\pi}_{(k+1)\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{(k+1)\delta} \right\| \right] \leq e^{-(c-KC_4(\delta))\delta} \mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{k\delta}\|] + C_5(\delta) e^{-c\delta}$$

Note that $\lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} C_4(\delta) = 1$, so we can choose δ sufficiently small such that $c - KC_4(\delta) > 0$ (since $K < c$) and therefore $e^{-(c-KC_4(\delta))\delta} < 1$. Let

$$r = \max(\|\pi_0 - \mu_0\|, \frac{C_5(\delta) e^{-c\delta}}{1 - e^{-(c-KC_4(\delta))\delta}})$$

By a straightforward mathematical induction we deduce that $\mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{k\delta}\|] \leq r$ for any $k \geq 0$. Assume that for $\mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{k\delta}\|] \leq r$, then

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \hat{\pi}_{(k+1)\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{(k+1)\delta} \right\| \right] \leq e^{-(c-KC_4(\delta))\delta} r + C_5(\delta) e^{-c\delta} \leq r.$$

Going back to (B17), for any $t \in [k\delta, (k+1)\delta]$, it holds that:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_t^\mu - \hat{\pi}_t\|] &\leq e^{-(c-KC_4(\delta)(t-k\delta))} \mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_{k\delta}^\mu - \hat{\pi}_{k\delta}\|] \\ &\quad + C_5(\delta) e^{-c\delta} \\ &\leq e^{-(c-KC_4(\delta)(t-k\delta))} r + C_5(\delta) e^{-c\delta} \\ &\leq r + C_5(\delta) e^{-c\delta} =: R \end{aligned}$$

Since R is independent of k , it follows that:

$$\sup_{t \geq 0} \mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\pi}_t^\mu - \hat{\pi}_t\|] \leq R.$$

□

Appendix C: Proofs in the linear case

Proposition 1. *If the conditions of Theorem 1 are satisfied then there exists a time $T > 0$ and a positive constant σ such that*

$$\|\mathcal{E}_t(0)\| \leq e^{-\sigma t}$$

for $t > T$.

Proof. From (28), the defining equation of $\mathcal{E}_t(R)$, we can write

$$d\mathcal{E}_t(0) = (A - P_\infty H)\mathcal{E}_t(0) dt + (P_\infty - P_t)H\mathcal{E}_t(0) dt.$$

To simplify notation, for the remainder of this proof we will write \mathcal{E}_t instead of $\mathcal{E}_t(0)$. Let $Q := A - P_\infty H$. Then it follows that,

$$\|\mathcal{E}_t\| \leq \|e^{Qt}\| \|\mathcal{E}_0\| + \int_0^t \|e^{Q(t-s)}\| \|P_s - P_\infty\| \|H\| \|\mathcal{E}_s\| ds.$$

Using Theorem 2, this simplifies to

$$\|\mathcal{E}_t\| \leq e^{\zeta(Q)t} \|\mathcal{E}_0\| + K_a \int_0^t \|e^{\zeta(Q)(t-s)}\| e^{-as} \|H\| \|\mathcal{E}_s\| ds. \quad (\text{C1})$$

Next for any T , let $\|\mathcal{E}_T\|^* = \sup_{0 \leq t \leq T} \|\mathcal{E}_t\|$. The proof of the theorem then follows in two steps. We first show that there exists a constant $M > 0$ independent of T such that $\|\mathcal{E}_T\|^* < M$ for all T . With the use of this constant and by evaluating the integral in (C1), it follows that there exists a constant $D > 0$ such that

$$\|\mathcal{E}_t\| \leq e^{\zeta(Q)t} \|\mathcal{E}_0\| + D e^{-at}$$

which implies the result since $\mathcal{E}_0 = 1$.

It remains prove existence of the constant M . To do so, fix T and then by using the fact that $\zeta(Q) < 0$ in (C1) and evaluating the last integral it follows that

$$\|\mathcal{E}_T\|^* \leq \|\mathcal{E}_0\| + K_a \frac{e^{\zeta(Q)T} - e^{-aT}}{\zeta(Q) + a} \|H\| \|\mathcal{E}_T\|^*$$

Then

$$f(T) \|\mathcal{E}_T\|^* \leq \|\mathcal{E}_0\|$$

with

$$f(T) = 1 - K_a \frac{e^{\zeta(Q)T} - e^{-aT}}{\zeta(Q) + a} \|H\|.$$

For large enough T , this function is positive and bounded above by 1. So we can pick \bar{T} large enough such that $f(\bar{T}) > \frac{1}{2}$. And so for $0 \leq T \leq \bar{T}$, $\|\mathcal{E}_T\|^*$ is bounded since it is continuous and for $T > \bar{T}$, $\|\mathcal{E}_T\|^* \leq 2\|\mathcal{E}_0\|$. So $M = \max(2\|\mathcal{E}_0\|, \|\mathcal{E}_{\bar{T}}\|^*)$ is an upper bound for $\sup_{t \geq 0} \|\mathcal{E}_t\|$. \square

Theorem 3. For any $n \geq 1$, if $\mathbb{E}(|X_0||\mathcal{Y}_t) < \infty$, then there exists $T > 0$ such that

$$\mathbb{W}_N(\pi_t, \pi_t^{0,0}) \leq \mathbb{E}(X_0|\mathcal{Y}_t)e^{-\sigma t} \quad (\text{C2})$$

for some $0 < \sigma < -\zeta(A - \psi_\infty H^\top H)$ and for all $t > T$.

Proof. We apply Lemma 1 with $\mu_1 = \text{Law}(X_0|Y_t)$, i.e. the conditional law of X_0 given Y_t , $M = G$ the Gaussian transition kernel (see Proposition 2 and the paragraph following this proposition for more details). We also have $\mu_2 = \delta_0$ since $\pi_t^{0,0}$ corresponds to the conditional law obtained when the Kallianpur-Striebel formula is initialised from a delta distribution centered as zero. With this, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{W}_N(\pi_t, \pi_t^{0,0}) \\ & \leq \int \delta_0(x) \frac{\pi_0(dx_0)Q_t(1)(x_0)}{\pi_0 Q_t(1)} \mathbb{W}_N(\delta_{x_0}G, \delta_x G) \quad (\text{C3}) \end{aligned}$$

Now consider the following random variables: W_1 is a d -dimensional random variable with normal distribution with mean vector 0 and covariance matrix being the identity matrix I , $X_1 = m_t(x_0, 0) + \psi_t(0)W_1$ and $X_2 = X_1 + (m_t(x, 0) - m_t(x_0, 0))$. Then the law of X_1 is $\delta_{x_0}G$ and that of X_2 is $\delta_x G$, respectively. Hence it follows from the definition of the Wasserstein distance that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{W}_N(\delta_{x_0}M, \delta_x M) & \leq \mathbb{E}(|X_1 - X_2|^n)^{\frac{1}{n}} \\ & = \mathbb{E}(|m_t(x, 0) - m_t(x_0, 0)|^n)^{\frac{1}{n}} \\ & = |x - x_0| \mathbb{E}(|\mathcal{E}_t(0)|^n)^{\frac{1}{n}}, \end{aligned}$$

where we used (29) in the last equality. Carrying out the integral in x first in C3 and using Proposition 1 we

obtain for large enough t :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{W}_N(\pi_t, \pi_t^{0,0}) & \leq \int \frac{\pi_0(dx_0)Q_t(1)(x_0)}{\pi_0 Q_t(1)} |x_0| e^{-\sigma t} \\ & = e^{-\sigma t} \mathbb{E}(|X_0||\mathcal{Y}_t). \quad (\text{C4}) \end{aligned}$$

The result then follows. \square

Theorem 4. Let $\phi : \mathbb{R}^N \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ be a bounded uniformly continuous function. Then if $\mathbb{E}(X_0^2|\mathcal{Y}_t) < \infty$ we have

$$|\pi_t(\phi) - \pi_t^{0,0}(\phi)| \rightarrow 0 \quad (\text{C5})$$

Proof. Using the representation given in Proposition 2 we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} & |\pi_t(\phi) - \pi_t^{0,0}(\phi)| \\ & \leq \int \frac{\pi_0(dx_0)Q_t(1)(x_0)}{\pi_0 Q_t(1)} |\pi_t^{x_0,0}(\phi) - \pi_t^{0,0}(\phi)| \quad (\text{C6}) \end{aligned}$$

Let $\Xi(a, P)$ denote a Gaussian random variable with mean a and covariance matrix P . With this notation, $\Xi(m_t(x_0, 0), \psi_t(0))$ has distribution $\pi_t^{x_0,0}$ and $\Xi(m_t(0, 0), \psi_t(0))$ has distribution $\pi_t^{0,0}$. We deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_t^{x_0,0}(\phi) - \pi_t^{0,0}(\phi) & = \mathbb{E}[\phi(\Xi(m_t(0, 0), \psi_t(0)) + \mathcal{E}_t(0)x_0) \\ & \quad + \phi(\Xi(m_t(0, 0), \psi_t(0)))], \end{aligned}$$

since

$$\begin{aligned} \Xi(m_t(x_0, 0), \psi_t(0)) & = \Xi(0, \psi_t(0)) + \mathcal{E}_t(0)x_0 + m_t(0, 0) \\ & = \Xi(m_t(0, 0), \psi_t(0)) + \mathcal{E}_t(0)x_0 \end{aligned}$$

Decomposing the integral in (C6) over the region where $|\mathcal{E}_t(0)x_0| \geq \delta$ and its complement, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |\pi_t(\phi) - \pi_t^{0,0}(\phi)| & \leq \sup_{|y-y'| \leq \delta} |\phi(y) - \phi(y')| \\ & \quad + 2\|\phi\|_\infty \mathbb{E}(1_{|\mathcal{E}_t(0)x_0| \geq \delta}|\mathcal{Y}_t) \\ & \leq \sup_{|y-y'| \leq \delta} |\phi(y) - \phi(y')| \quad (\text{C7}) \\ & \quad + \frac{2\|\phi\|_\infty}{\delta^2} (\mathcal{E}_t(0))^2 \mathbb{E}(X_0^2|\mathcal{Y}_t). \end{aligned}$$

The last term converges to 0 as $t \rightarrow \infty$ by 1. Then choosing δ small enough so that $|\phi(y) - \phi(y')| < \epsilon$ and making ϵ arbitrarily small gives the result. \square